

Synthesis of Some New 5-Mercapto 3-Substituted Quinazolone-s-Triazoles ; Their Reaction with Dibromo Alkanes

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5-Mercapto 3-substituted quinazolone-s-triazoles(VII) obtained by the cyclisation of corresponding quinazolone thiosemicarbazides(VI) were reacted with 1,2-dibromoethane and 1,3-dibromopropane to yield 2-substituted 5,6-dihydrothiazolo[3,2-b]-s-triazoles(VIII) and 2-substituted 5H-6,7-dihydro-s-triazolo[3,2-b][1,3]-thiazines(IX) respectively. These compounds were also screened for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria alternata*, *Drechslera papendorfii* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Only quinazolone thiosemicarbazides(VI) showed measurable activity.

CONTINUED interest in incorporating a quinazolone nucleus, capable of exhibiting hypnotic¹, anticonvulsant², analgesic³, antifungal and antibacterial⁴ properties led Devani *et al* to synthesise some 2,3,4-trisubstituted quinazolone sulphonyl thioureas⁵. These were tested for their antibacterial activity. Some 2-amino-4(3H)-quinazolones have also been reported to possess fungicidal activity⁶. On the other hand, various thiosemicarbazides⁷ and their cyclised products, oxadiazoles and s-triazoles⁸ have been reported to possess antibacterial and antifungal activity. Recently some thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-triazoles and s-triazolo[3,2-b][1,3]-thiazines have been synthesised and evaluated for their fungicidal activity⁹.

These findings prompted us to synthesise some new quinazolones by incorporating a heterocyclic ring at position 3 of quinazolone nucleus with a view to study their antifungal activity. Accordingly 5-mercapto 3-substituted quinazolone-s-triazoles (VII) were obtained by refluxing corresponding thiosemicarbazides(VI) with 8% sodium hydroxide solution. The reaction of 1,2-dibromoethane with (VII) in anhydrous ethanol gave 2-quinazolone 5,6-dihydrothiazolo[3,2-b]-s-triazoles(VIII).

The structure of compounds (VIII) has been supported by their correct analytical data (Table 3). The IR spectra of compounds (VIII) showed characteristic absorption bands at 1675-1668 cm⁻¹ (endocyclic C=O), 1600-1590 cm⁻¹ (C=N), 1505-1440 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretching), 1365-1320 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C) and 2955-2900 cm⁻¹ (C-CH₃).

Similarly when compounds (VII) were refluxed with 1,3-dibromo-propane in anhydrous ethanol furnished 2-substituted quinazolone 5H-6,7-dihydro-s-triazolo[3,2-b][1,3]-thiazines(IX).

The structure of compounds (IX) has been supported by their correct analytical data (Table 4) and IR spectra showed absorption bands at 1677-1665 cm⁻¹ (endocyclic C=O), 1595-1585 cm⁻¹ (C=N), 1510-1450 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretching), 1390-1350 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C) and 2950-2920 cm⁻¹ (C-CH₃).

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The IR absorption spectra were determined in KBr pallets on Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer.

Substituted anthranilic acids(I)¹⁰⁻¹², acetan-
thranil(II)¹³, ethyl glycine ester(III)¹⁴, quinazolone
esters(IV)¹⁵, and quinazolone hydrazides(V)¹⁵ were
prepared by following the known methods.

Quinazolone thiosemicarbazides(VI)

A mixture of appropriate quinazolone hydrazide
(V) (0.01 mole), potassium thiocyanate (0.01 mole),
concentrated HCl (0.8 ml) and water (20 ml) was
refluxed for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was
cooled to obtain the corresponding quinazolone
thiosemicarbazide, which was filtered, washed with
water and crystallised from suitable solvents. The
results are recorded in Table 1. The IR spectrum
of 2-methyl-3-acetyl thiosemicarbazide-4-quinazolone
showed characteristic absorption bands at 1690 cm⁻¹
(endocyclic C=O), 1658 cm⁻¹ (CONH), 1600 cm⁻¹
(C=N), 1470 cm⁻¹, 1445 cm⁻¹ and 1390 cm⁻¹ (C-N
stretching), 1240 cm⁻¹ (C=S), 3380 cm⁻¹ and 3200
cm⁻¹ (N-H stretching) and 2910 cm⁻¹ ($\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$)

TABLE-1. QUINAZOLONE THIOSEMICARBAZIDES(VI)

Sl. No.	X	X'	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Found / Calcd. %N %S	
1.**	H	H	50	290	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	23.87 24.06	10.02 10.99
2.*	H	Br	47	245	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	18.24 18.92	8.04 8.65
3.**	Br	Br	52	304	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	14.93 15.59	6.75 7.13
4.*	H	I	42	249	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ IN ₂ O ₂ S	15.89 16.79	6.97 7.67
5.**	Cl	Cl	44	316	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	19.28 19.44	8.35 8.89

* Crystallised from ethanol, ** Crystallised from acetic acid

5-Mercapto 3-substituted quinazolone-s-triazoles (VII)

Appropriate quinazolone thiosemicarbazide(VI)
(0.01 mole) in 8% sodium hydroxide solution was
refluxed for about 3 hrs. The reaction mixture was
cooled and acidified with dilute acetic acid. The
precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with
water, dried and crystallised from ethanol. The
results are recorded in Table 2. The IR spectrum
of 5-mercapto 3-(6',8'-dibromo quinazolone)-s-
triazole showed absorption bands at 1690 cm⁻¹
(endocyclic C=O), 1590 cm⁻¹ (C=N), 1480 cm⁻¹,
1445 cm⁻¹ and 1420 cm⁻¹ (C-N stretching), 3470
cm⁻¹ and 3360 cm⁻¹ (N-H stretching), 740 cm⁻¹
(C-S) and 2910 cm⁻¹ (S-H and $\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$).

TABLE-2. 5-MERCAPTO 3-SUBSTITUTED QUINAZOLONE-S-TRIAZOLES(VII)

Sl. No.	X	X'	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Found / Calcd. %N %S	
6.	H	H	47	310	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS	25.12 25.64	11.39 11.72
7.	H	Br	43	199	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ BrN ₂ OS	19.32 19.89	8.67 9.09
8.	Br	Br	55	241	C ₁₂ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ OS	15.89 16.24	6.94 7.42
9.	H	I	45	189	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ IN ₂ OS	16.98 17.54	7.58 8.02
10.	Cl	Cl	48	289	C ₁₂ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ OS	19.04 20.47	9.69 9.36

2-Substituted quinazolone 5,6-dihydrothiazolo [3,2-b]-s-triazoles(VIII)

A mixture of appropriate 5-mercapto 3-substituted
quinazolone-s-triazole(VII) (0.01 mole) 1,2-dibro-
moethane (0.01 mole) in anhydrous ethanol (60 ml)
was refluxed on steam bath for 36-40 hrs. The
cooled reaction mixture was neutralised with
ammonium hydroxide. The product that separated
out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised
from ethanol. The results are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE-3. 2-SUBSTITUTED QUINAZOLONE 5,6-DIHYDROTHIAZOLO 3,2-b-s-TRIAZOLES(VIII)

Sl. No.	X	X'	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Found / Calcd. %N %S	
11.	H	H	38	249	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₆ OS	22.90 23.41	9.20 10.70
12.	H	Br	32	117	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ BrN ₆ OS	18.13 18.52	7.56 8.46
13.	Br	Br	44	211	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₆ OS	14.86 15.32	6.92 7.00
14.	H	I	39	238	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ IN ₆ OS	16.32 16.47	7.19 7.33
15.	Cl	Cl	41	259	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₆ OS	18.57 19.02	7.92 8.69

2-Substituted quinazolone 5H-6,7-dihydro-s-triazolo [3,2-b] [1,3]-thiazines(IX)

A mixture of appropriate 5-mercapto 3-substi-
tuted quinazolone-s-triazole(VII) (0.01 mole) and
1,3-dibromopropane (0.01 mole) was refluxed in
anhydrous ethanol (60 ml) for about 40 hrs. The
cooled reaction mixture was neutralised with
ammonium hydroxide. The product that separated
out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised
from ethanol. The results are recorded in Table 4.

Antifungal activity

All the compounds synthesised were screened for
their antifungal activity against *Alternaria alternata*,
Drechslera papendorffii and *Helminthosporium oryzae*
at concentrations 2%, 0.2%, 0.02% and 0.002% (W/V)
by Paper-disc plate method¹⁴. Only quinazolone

TABLE—4. 2-SUBSTITUTED QUINAZOLONE 5H-6, 7-DIHYDRO-S-TRIAZOLO[3, 2.b][1, 3]-THIAZINES(IX)

Sl. No.	X	X'	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	Found / Calcd.	
						%N	%S
16.	H	H	41	172	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ OS	22.02 22.36	9.92 10.22
17.	H	Br	34	278	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ BrN ₅ OS	16.58 17.86	7.56 8.16
18.	Br	Br	47	262	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ Br ₂ N ₅ OS	14.29 14.86	5.89 6.79
19.	H	I	36	263	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ IN ₅ OS	14.98 15.95	6.94 2.29
20.	Cl	Cl	39	221	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₅ OS	17.88 18.32	7.95 8.38

thiosemicarbazides(VI) listed in Table 1 were found to possess measurable antifungal activity against all the three fungi at concentration 2%, while the compounds listed in Tables 2, 3 and 4 were completely devoid of antifungal activity.

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